

MADRAS

D5.11 Communication Activities

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Executive summary

Eurecat is responsible for designing and implementing MADRAS communication strategy through its Research Communications Office, but all consortium partners will be involved in it. This deliverable detail the communication activities done during the first three months of the project and the plan for the rest of the project. Communication activities aim at promoting the project results to as many relevant actors as possible in order to position the project into the professional world and create bridges for citizen awareness and participation, in order to ensure societal relevance and acceptability and promote technological education.

The channels considered within the communication activities plan are: designing the project's corporate identity, social media channels, official website, promotional materials (brochure, flyers, etc.), media relations and email marketing.

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List of abbreviations

<i>EUT</i>	<i>Eurecat</i>
<i>IME</i>	<i>In Mold Electronics</i>
<i>OLAE</i>	<i>Organic and Large Area Electronics</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>VCI</i>	<i>Visual Corporative Image</i>

Introduction

MADRAS is a 3-year research project aiming to demonstrate a materials-driven improvement of OLAE devices, developing a high-speed manufacturing methodology in a scalable competitive process, which is In Mould Electronics (IME).

The project also addresses the need for innovative and industrial manufacturing processes for the development of robust series of plastronics products. Building on an already established technology as plastic injection will facilitate a faster up taking.

In addition, MADRAS project proposes two products for persons' authentication market and smart manufacturing that will show a step forward towards digitisation and Internet of Things for its contribution to the sustainable deployment of smart products for consumer use.

Eurecat is the partner leader of **Task 5.7 Communication Activities**, but all consortium partners will be involved in it. Task 5.7 has the objective to create and provide all the communication materials needed for conveying the project to a broad group of users. This task includes the design and execution of MADRAS communication activities in a wide range of channels. We understand communication as a continuous process that needs to be seen as essential for the results of the project, itself.

It is worth noting that **in order to protect the commercial interests of the participants, the publication of the materials will be selective**, except for submission of contractually required reports and information to the Commission. In this case, partners decide which part of the projects' information is to be protected by copyright or trade secrets and which part of the above information is suitable for communicating widely.

All the actions will consider EC recommendations explained in the Participant Portal H2020 Online Manual section on project communication.

(http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm).

Key messages

The communication plan messages have been carefully designed and tailored with each of the stakeholders in mind and will be adapted to the different MADRAS communication channels. The messages go together with the main objectives and translate the possibilities and strength of the research done during the project.

The following messages will be evolved in pertinent messages for all audiences, both specialized and non-specialized, in a way that they can understand actions and results of MADRAS project.

The messages that MADRAS will address to stakeholders include:

- MADRAS project will develop **new materials and manufacturing processes** for a **scalable production** in an industrial level of **organic and large-area electronic (OLAE) devices**.

- MADRAS project aims to **boost the production of organic and large-area electronics (OLAE)** by establishing a high-speed manufacturing methodology that allows their mass production.
- MADRAS novel production process will be **validated in a biometric photosensor for user identification** of a scooter-sharing company and a **geotracking flexible tag** for the packaging and logistics sector.
- **Organic and Large Area Electronics (OLAE)** is a new branch of electronics that allows to **develop thinner, more power-efficient, flexible, and lightweight** electronic devices made of carbon-based materials.
- The project is funded by the European Commission, who believes that MADRAS will contribute in **increasing Europe’s competitiveness and leadership in the production of OLAE products**.

Channels

For communication activities, MADRAS project will use a wide range of channels and actions, from promotional materials to media relations, using email marketing campaigns, setting up a website and building a community of interested users around the project (see Figure1).

Besides the ones mentioned, all partners will make use of their channels (website, presence on Social Media and corporate newsletters / publications) to communicate news about MADRAS and reach a broader audience.

Figure 1: MADRAS communication channels

Audience

The audience for Communication action is the same as identified for Dissemination and Exploitation, as broken down in several main stakeholder groups below.

The process of identifying the key persons and entities that embody this stakeholder consideration has already begun, developing a more detailed list to be the target for all communication activities. All stakeholders with a professional Twitter account will be followed by MADRAS’s Twitter.

For that purpose, an excel file to record the stakeholders identified has been prepared and stored in MADRAS internal collaborative platform.

Industrial community	Scientific, academic community	Policy makers	Society in general
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consumers of OLAE devices / printed electronics products in the IoT, packaging, appliances, transport and wearables sector, among others. • Companies in the OLAE devices value chain (inks and materials' suppliers, transport / logistic companies, industrial manufacturers...) • End user industries incorporating upgraded plastic components in their products (packaging, safety, robotics, mobility,...) • Industrial associations and clusters (eg. Functional Print Cluster, Business Cluster Semiconductors Netherlands, Etronics (Estonia), Organic Electronics Saxony (Germany), Hellenic Organic Electronics Association (Greece)) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universities and technology center researching in functional printing, organic electronics, conductive and semiconductive materials, sensors, etc. • Vocational / training centres. • Attendants to scientific conferences and workshops covering the project's field (LOPEC, DRUPA, IDTechEx, Innolae, OE-A..) • Members of related projects (eg. SmartEEs2, InSCOPE) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elected officials at EU, national, regional and local level. • Policy makers • International and European platforms, associations and agencies (eg. OE-A (EU), AFELIM (France) 3D NEO (Spain), BPIF (UK), TC 119 Printed Electronics.) • Standardisation bodies and technical committees. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Media / bloggers. • Individual citizens.

Figure 2: MADRAS stakeholders

Communication activities

1. Project's corporate visual identity image

Eurecat, as the leader of Communication task has developed MADRAS's Corporate Visual Identity, including the project's logo, a Power Point template, Word templates for project activities and a visual identity standards guidebook, defining and outlining how to use identifying elements pertaining to MADRAS including logos, colours, fonts, stationery and graphic resources. In addition, it sets a design layout for project promotional materials to be developed in the following months.

See **D5.9 Visual Corporate Image** for more information on the elements designed.

Figure 3: MADRAS full colour logo

2. Public Website

Figure 5: Graphic resources for designing project's materials

The project

website (www.madras-project.eu) has been launched in June 2020 as defined in **Deliverable**

5.10 Public Project Website - Figure 4: View of some pages of the project's deliverable template

Project

Website to serve as the main information platform for users interested in knowing more about

MADRAS, displaying the project’s basic information, objectives, demonstrators and expected results.

Furthermore, the website is the central point of entry for all public material, including public results and deliverables and give access to MADRAS Social Media.

The website will be regularly updated with dissemination activities, media appearances and new deliverables.

Considering that different authors might update the site, a Wordpress Content Management System has been adopted by Eurecat, to easily and quickly publish the content. The website has been optimised for browsing on tablets and smart phones, so the website has been developed using a responsive design approach.

2.1 Website structure

Current website structure looks like the following:

Figure 6: MADRAS website menu structure

Website content and structure will be updated regularly during the project by EUT, including the creation of new pages and updating the news & events page with articles in order to generate content to feed the project’s social media and increase the traffic to the website. News articles will be categorized in self-explanatory categories to facilitate filtering.

2.2 Managing and updating policy

The website has been developed by Eurecat with the inputs received from all partners in the consortium.

Public deliverables will be made public in PDF format in the website results page once submitted and approved by the European Commission. Regarding confidential deliverables, an executive summary will be published after submission to the European Commission portal.

2.2.1 Blog posts

As detailed in **D5.10 - Public Project Website**, partners will be required to contribute to the maintenance of the news section during project execution, following guidelines to be prepared. Partners' blog articles will be disseminated widely across project channels.

Blog posts increase the website traffic and are a powerful dissemination tool of project tasks and knowledge generated, as well as help position MADRAS partners as experts in one field of expertise.

3. Promotional materials

EUT will be in charge of the creation of all visual material to support dissemination activities such as conferences, congresses, or project events. MADRAS project will create communication materials such as an info sheet (M5, updated by M30), a brochure (M5, updated by M30), a roll-up (M5), poster layout (M4) and a general project presentation (M6).

These materials will serve as the project's business card and will be distributed as widely as possible, including the general public, conferences, workshops and other events, from the beginning of the project.

All materials will be stored digitally in the project's internal repository and on the project's website for broader dissemination. Promotional materials will be regularly updated according to the project's developments.

Figure 7: Design proposals of MADRAS' promotional materials

Furthermore, to communicate MADRAS project and results **several videos** will be produced. The proposed videos to be produced are:

- **M12 - Animated Video:** MADRAS animated video with motion graphics describing the project main objectives and expected outputs. The video, lasting about one minute, will address a non-specialized audience and aims to be used as a quick presentation of the project in events. The video will also be shared on social media and featured on the website.
- **M12-M24- Video capsules:** Short interviews to project partners about topics related to the project (novel materials developed, IME technology, methodology, demonstrators, etc.). EUT will decide on the topics of interest for the audience of the project and will prepare the questions to be sent in advance to produce short video capsules to be shared on social media. The videos will be produced during a consortium meeting or recorded via Teams (TBC) and edited by EUT.
- **M18-M36- Production Process MADRAS demonstrators:** Video of the production process of each of the products validated with MADRAS technology. EUT will coordinate the videos. Partners will be in charge of recording images during the products' production in their facilities, which will be edit and them.
- **M1-M36- Experiments, production processes:** short videos produced by partners conducting MADRAS tests / experiments, production processes for Social Media.

All videos will be uploaded on the project's YouTube channel and website and will have a clear reference to EC support via the Horizon 2020 programme.

On the other hand, a **pack of MADRAS's project images for partner's free use** will be made available through the project's shared repository. Partners will be also be able to contribute with non-confidential and free-to-use images to be used for internal and external presentations of project-related materials.

4. Social Media

Eurecat will manage MADRAS's social media accounts and its contents described hereinafter. MADRAS project will count usage of a **Twitter Channel**, [@MADRAS_Project](#), and a **YouTube channel**, account to be created as soon as the first project video is available.

On the other hand, **partners will contribute to spreading the word on their corporate and personal Social Media channels**, including accounts in Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn or Instagram.

The project coordinator will be in charge of notifying the European Commission about possible content of interest to be published through its official social media channels and, whenever possible, will promote the use of social media complicities between MADRAS and its sister projects (SmartEEs, PeroCUBE, HI-ACCURACY, RoLA-FLEX, etc.).

4.1 Twitter

Twitter is the 2.0 tool most used by the European Commission to now disseminate the H2020 program, so the creation of an account has full meaning. The account will be managed by EUT with the support of project partners for the correct management of the account.

MADRAS project's main objective on Twitter is to raise awareness on flexible electronics, OLAE devices production processes, benefits and new materials allowing the development of devices by printing techniques with increased robustness, while reducing their cost and environmental impact, as well as promoting the project's methodology / industrial production process to key stakeholders and the broader audience.

Twitter will also be used to connect with EU institutions and related projects. Twitter allows us to reach directly targeted audiences from validated professional accounts.

4.1.1 Account management

Eurecat will create a **regular content plan** to be disseminated through Twitter. All consortium partners can propose contents (text, images, videos...) to be distributed for this channel and can spread the word through their own channels.

MADRAS's Communication Leader Eurecat will use **Hootsuite** for programming tweets and shorten URLs, a management tool that facilitates the publication of contents and easy monitors the activity on social media.

Comments and answers will be managed manually, in order to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content.

Figure 8: MADRAS Twitter account

4.1.2 Strategy

When creating and publishing content on the networks about the project, Eurecat and the rest of the partners will consider the following recommendations in order to maximize the impact of the messages.

The strategy mixes marketing content, branding, and influence actions to maximise MADRAS' project impact and encourage market uptake, to secure a critical mass of early adopters among consumers.

4.1.2.1 Content strategy

- **Disseminate project activities:** the organization of meetings, reviews, trainings, workshops, events, and milestones including text and photos if possible.
- **Content curation:** sharing news on OLAE, printed electronics, flexible electronics, conductive and semi-conductive materials, IME, etc.

- Disseminate audio-visual and promotional materials made for the project (to make the project more accessible/understandable).
- Sharing news and blog posts published in the website to increase traffic to the website.
- To increase the reach of the tweets, it is proposed the frequent use of the following hashtags, usual in other areas within the scope of the project: #MADRAS #MADRASproject #ResearchImpactEu #Horizon2020 #H2020 #OLAE #IME #InMouldElectronics #Electronics #PrintedElectronics #FlexibleElectronics #FunctionalPrinting #bioelectronics #sensors #OrganicElectronics #EmergingElectronics # #substrates #materials #inks #plastronics #PlastronicProducts #Conductivelnk #photovoltaics #FEW #InMold #photosensor #Printed antenna #Smart Tag #Silver nanowires #Nanocellulose #Tungsten oxide
- Mention project partners ([@Eurecat_News](#), [@Arjocreatives](#), [@UniPardubice](#), [@Uwinloc](#), [@Tecnopackaging](#), [@NormasUNE](#) [@HolstCentre](#), [@infinityPV](#), [@cooltra](#), [@genesink](#)) when publishing news about them to promote likes and retweets from partners.
- Mention and retweet content from projects funded under the same topic or working on the same field with a twitter account (PeroCUBE [@CubePero](#), Cornet [@CornetH2020](#), SmartEEs 2 [@SmartEEsEU](#), Wearplex [@wearplex](#), 5E [@5E_project](#), RealNano [@RealnanoP](#), InSCOPE [@InSCOPE_EU](#), INNPAPER [@INNPAPER_EU](#), etc.)
- Mention and retweet content from EU OLAE / Printed Electronics associations / platforms (OE-A [@OEOnline](#), HOPE-A [@H_OPE](#), Functional Printing Cluster [@ClusterFPrint](#), etc.).

4.1.2.2 Branding strategy

- Twitter covering about fairs, trade shows, congresses, and events where MADRAS participates using the official hashtag of the event (e.g. LOPEC #LOPEC2021, DRUPA #drupa, International Symposium on Flexible Organic Electronics #ISFOE etc.).
- MADRAS Twitter official account will be referenced in the partner's corporate accounts for a broader reach of the project.

4.1.2.3 Influencers strategy

- Regularly mention [@EU_H2020](#) [@EuScienceInnov](#) [@CORDIS_EU](#) [@EU_commission](#) [@OE-A](#) [@SEMIEurope](#) [@Electronics_EU](#) in order to get a bigger impact when project news or information about results is published.
- Identify and mention influencers in the field of OLAE, In-Mould Electronics, flexible electronics and printed electronics, among other topics.
- Identification of stakeholder's accounts to promote follow-back and to increase the number of MADRAS followers.
- Media will be mentioned if they are publishing information about the project.

4.1.3 Following and followers

Our reputation on Twitter depends on the number of users we follow. There must be a balanced number between our followers and the users we follow. Otherwise, it is considered that the tool is being misused, since the objective is to share knowledge bidirectionally.

Therefore, MADRAS will follow people and organizations related to the project's topic (OLAE, printing electronics, flexible electronics, etc.). At the first stage of the project, MADRAS' Twitter account will follow all project partners, as well as institutions, centres and professionals in the field of the project, which will be identified during the first months of the project. The social media accounts, as well as the Twitter profiles of reference covering the project topic will also be followed.

We will avoid followers with an offensive avatar (for example, pornographic, racist) or spammers, which we will block.

4.1.4 First battery of tweets

See below the **first battery of tweets** proposed to be scheduled for publication for the months of July - September, with the main objective to **bring traffic to the website** and **promote the project's main two concepts**: OLAE and IME. The twitter posts are in line with the key messages to be targeted to the main stakeholder groups.

New batteries for Twitter will be prepared periodically to inform about the project developments. Third-party content on project topics and blog posts will be also published with regularity in combination with tweets on based on project information.

Goal:
Promote and bring traffic to the website
 #MADRAS partners will develop a set of new #materials to be used as #inks with improved electrical and optical properties for the production of flexible #OLAE products #ConductiveInks
 Find out more: **LINK: www.madras-project.eu**

#MADRAS @EU_H2020 funded project develops new #materials and manufacturing processes for a scalable production in an industrial level of organic and large-area #electronic devices #OLAE
 Find out more - **LINK: www.madras-project.eu**

#OLAE is a new branch of #electronics allowing thinner, more power-efficient, flexible and lightweight devices

#MADRAS #H2020 project will validate a novel technology for their mass production combining #PrintedElectronics and #InMouldElectronics **LINK: www.madras-project.eu**

Goal:

Promote and bring traffic to the website

#MADRASproject novel production process will be validated in a biometric photosensor for user identification and a geotracking flexible tag for the packaging and logistics sector

More information **LINK:** <https://madras-project.eu/demonstrators/>

#MADRAS project innovation lays in the capacity of creating new #PlastronicProducts, as well as to include new technology into traditional products with seamless integration #Plastronics

About the project **LINK:** <https://madras-project.eu/about-us/>

MADRAS develops #AdvancedMaterials to be promptly processed via #IME to fabricate a new generation of #plastronic products with enhanced properties for more affordable and durable #OLAE-based devices

LINK: <https://madras-project.eu/about-us>

4 novel materials are being developed within #MADRAS @EU_H2020 project for the development of devices by printing techniques with [ICON] increased robustness and [ICON] reduced cost and environmental impact **LINK:** <https://madras-project.eu/about-us>

#MADRAS #H2020 will contribute in increasing @EU_commission competitiveness and leadership in the production of #OLAE products via #InMouldElectronics #PrintedElectronics

Find out more about the project **LINK:** www.madras-project.eu

Who is behind #MADRAS project? A consortium of 12 partners from 5 European countries expert in #PrintedElectronics #OLAE #IME #FlexibleElectronics **LINK:** <https://madras-project.eu/about-us/partners/> **IMAGE** with logos and location of all partners

To enable the future market deployment of flexible #OLAE-based products

12 partners from 5 European Countries [EU FLAG ICON] work together in #MADRAS project to develop low cost and reliable materials for a high-volume production of flexible plastronic products + **LINK:** www.madras-project.eu

Goal:
Promote and raise awareness on OLAE

.@IDTechEx forecasts that #OLAE devices market will more than double in size over the next ten years growing from \$41.2 Billion in 2020 to \$74 billion in 2030

Learn more about #OrganicElectronics and its market **LINK:** <https://madras-project.eu/olae/>

#OLAE technology is a new branch of #electronics that works on carbon-based materials

It allow to develop thinner, more power-efficient, flexible and lightweight devices that are [ICON] cheaper and more [ICON] environmentally friendly **LINK:** <https://madras-project.eu/olae/>

Goal:
Promote and raise awareness on IME

#InMouldElectronics will be employed in #MADRAS project as an integration process, targeting #recyclability, and as a fabrication process of four novel #AdvancedMaterials

Find out more about this technology **LINK:** <https://madras-project.eu/in-mould-electronics/>

#InMouldElectronics #IME combines the #FunctionalPrinting of electronics and the hybridisation of electronic components with traditional plastic transformation processes

Know more about the manufacturing process **LINK:** <https://madras-project.eu/in-mould-electronics/>

#InMouldElectronics manufacturing steps include

[ICON 1] Printing

[ICON 2] Hybridisation

[ICON 3] Thermoforming

[ICON 4] Injection

More information **LINK:** <https://madras-project.eu/in-mould-electronics/>

4.1.5 Analytics

A profile in Twitter Analytics will be activated in order to measure Twitter’s KPIs (please view Communication KPIs section for more information) and other data about the account activity. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

4.2 YouTube

The European Commission has recommended the use of resources as the storytelling for putting objectives and results of the research projects closer to the general public. This narrative technique is based on the narrative of a story and it is used on marketing strategies to better reach users thanks to a character and a plot.

Following these recommendations, the videos produced within the project (M12 and M36) will be published in a **YouTube channel** and will be shared on the website and project's Twitter for a broader impact.

On the other hand, the account will serve as a content **repository of all audio-visual content that may be produced during the project.**

4.3 Partners Channels

Each partner will transmit MADRAS news and results through their personal and corporate social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and Instagram), including press releases, notices about events, promotional materials and other contents published on www.madras-project.eu or in MADRAS' twitter account.

MADRAS's partners impact in social media channels will reach more than **29,300 users on Twitter**, more than **43,300 on LinkedIn** and more than **24.068 Facebook** followers.

The corporate accounts to be used are:

Table 1: Partners Social Media Channels

PARTNER	Facebook	Twitter	LinkedIn
EUT	https://www.facebook.com/Eurecatorg/	@Eurecat_news	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eurecat/
GNK	NA	@genesink	https://www.linkedin.com/company/genesink/
AWF	NA	@ArjoCreatives	https://www.linkedin.com/company/arjowiggins-creative-papers/
UPA	https://www.facebook.com/fchtupa/	@UniPardubice	https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-pardubice/
COC	NA	NA	NA
UWL	https://www.facebook.com/UWINLOC/	@Uwinloc	https://www.linkedin.com/company/uwinloc/

TNG	https://www.facebook.com/Tecnopackaging/	@Tecnopackaging	https://www.linkedin.com/company/tecnopackaging/
UNE	NA	@NormasUNE	https://www.linkedin.com/company/une-asociaci%C3%B3n-espa%C3%B1ola-de-normalizaci%C3%B3n/
TNO	NA	@Holstcentre	https://www.linkedin.com/company/holst-centre/
ERC	https://www.facebook.com/eticasconsult/	NA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eticas-research-&-consulting/
INF	https://www.facebook.com/infinityPV/	@infinitypv	https://www.linkedin.com/company/infinitypv-aps
COOLTRA	https://www.facebook.com/CooltraMotos	@Cooltra	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cooltra-motos-s-l- /

4.3.1 Guidelines for publishing about the project on Social Media

Partners are suggested to apply the following recommendations when communication about the project on Social Media:

- Use #MADRAS #MADRASproject hashtag or mention @MADRAS_project if you are using Twitter.
- Mention project partners to increase your reach
- Share links to project website / materials
- Communicate your role/task on the project

Partners can also use the guidelines prepared for the project's Twitter when publishing about the project in Social Media.

5. Media relations

Press releases will be **written and sent at regular intervals throughout the project** focusing on the release of research results, meetings, attendance at specialised events, conferences, etc. and connected with newsworthy initiatives when possible.

All **press releases will be distributed among partners in English**, who, after providing feedback, will be able to adapt them in their corporate language and make them circulate throughout their communication channels and sent to their media database.

Apart from consortium press releases, country-focused press releases or press releases oriented for a specific stakeholder group can be elaborated by partners, after informing the Project Coordinator. Also, partners can consider interview-offerings and a press conference at the end of the project to show the main project results to media.

In the framework of the project, a **database with the contact details of partners' communication officers** will be created, to facilitate the review of the media materials, coordinate the sending of the press releases and increase impact.

On the other hand, a **database with specialized media covering OLAE, IME and Printing Electronics** will be created, primarily with outlets located in the partner's countries. Communication Leader Eurecat will contact key specialized media and include them in their media database.

5.1 List of identified outlets of interest

Partners have identified the following specialised media outlets as relevant to promote MADRAS outputs:

- **Printed Electronics Now Magazine** - <https://www.printedelectronicsnow.com/issues/2020-02-24/> US publication on flexible, organic and printed electronics industry (including sensors, displays and touch screens, RFID and NFC tags and labels, solar cells and batteries), conductive inks, raw materials, equipment or current research.
- **CIE Magazine** - <https://www.cieonline.co.uk/> CIE provides editorial content from features covering every aspect of the electronics industry to comments and market predictions from key players in the industry plus the latest products and innovations.
- **Electronics Magazine** - <http://www.connectingindustry.com/electronics/> News in electronic components, products, equipment & services.
-
- **5E Digital Showcase**- an **online** platform to increase visibility of innovative European electronics products, in particular products whose innovative character builds on Nano-Electronics, **Flexible & Wearable Electronics and Electronic Smart Systems** <https://5e-project.eu/2020/04/03/5e-digital-showcase/>
- **Printed Electronics World** - <https://www.printedelectronicsworld.com/> Printed Electronics World provides daily updates of the latest industry developments. Launched in May 2007, the portal covers the progress to printed electronics in all its forms - from transistor circuits to power, sensors, displays, materials and manufacturing.

- **MundoPlast** - <https://mundoplast.com/> Spanish specialised magazine reporting on the plastics sector: transformers and end product manufacturers, engineering, manufacturers and distributors of raw materials, machinery, molds and equipment, etc.
- **PlásticosModernos** - <http://www.revistaplasticosmodernos.es/> Spanish specialised magazine being edited since 1950 on the latest developments and R+D in polymeric materials.
- **OPE Journal** - <https://oe-a.org/en/viewer/-/v2article/render/26804486> Professional magazine (printed and online) for the organic and printed electronics industry with over 11,000 copies circulated globally. It is published four times a year and each issue is centered on a special topic in the field of organic and printed electronics, ranging from energy and packaging, to displays and Internet of Things.

5.2 Press release plan

An initial calendar of press releases to be written is as follows:

Table 2: Press release plan

MADRAS press release plan		Partner responsible
M3	First press release on the project	EUT
M24	Novel materials developed	EUT, AWF, GNK, COC, UPA
M33	Geotracking flexible tag	EUT, UWL
M33	Biometric Photosensor	EUT, ERC
M36	Final press release project results	EUT

6. Newsletters

News and updated of the project will be distributed via newsletters to ensure that all stakeholders are regularly informed about the latest project's developments. **Six newsletters will be issued**, one at the end of the first year (M13) and then regularly every 3/6 months (M18, M25, M30, M33, M36).

The **database of subscribers will be built during the whole project**, putting the main efforts during the first months of the project to have an acceptable number of subscribers for the first release.

On **M10**, prior to the first issue, a **newsletter template** to be followed will be produced.

The MADRAS newsletter will be disseminated via links on social media, direct ad hoc emails to professional contacts of the consortium partners and via browsing the MADRAS website, where all newsletter issues will be stored.

Furthermore, information about MADRAS project will be included to partners' newsletters or corporate publications, such as Eurecat's monthly corporate newsletter addressed to external audience, with more than 15,000 subscribers.

6.1 Platform

Eurecat proposes [e-goi](#) as the email platform to be used for the newsletter design, sending and stats monitoring. E-goi allows to easily create newsletters of varying types and then provides simple options for sharing them on social networks such as Twitter or Facebook.

6.2 Audience

Subscribers will be gained progressively during the whole project via a **sign-up form published on the website homepage and promoted via social media channels**. Partners will also be required to promote the newsletter sign up form on their communication channels.

The sign-up form will comply with GDPR, linking to the newsletter privacy policy and informing the user about its right to cancel the subscription at any moment.

Subscriptions and De-subscriptions will be managed automatically via e-goi,¹ the email marketing online platform that will be used for sending the newsletters. E-goi will act as MADRAS data processor. Data collected through the sign-up form will be used for the exclusive purpose of sending subscribers information related to the project and will never be passed to third-party companies, unless there is a legal obligation to do so.

Though the newsletter, **MADRAS partners aim at reaching the main stakeholders groups defined for exploitation**, specially the scientific and academic community and industrial community.

6.3 Content

Eurecat will be responsible for the content of newsletters issues, with the contribution of all partners. Before every publication, partners will be contacted for inputs (e.g. information on project tasks or events where the project was presented).

The content of the newsletters will follow project milestones (development of novel materials, manufacturing steps of MADRAS demonstrators, etc.). Every issue will include the appropriate references to H2020 and contact details (email and link to the website and social media).

6.4 Analytics

Newsletter analytics, such as open rate or click through rate, will be **extracted through e-goi**. Statistics will be checked 3 days after sending the newsletter and will be analysed in order to see which articles worked best and be able to improve the newsletter impact in the following issues.

¹ <https://www.e-goi.com/>

Communication activities management

1. Requirements

For all communication materials produced every project member should follow the description below to be in line with EU regulations described in the Grant Agreement:

According to the Grant Agreement “*unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:*

- a. *Display the EU emblem and*
- b. *Include the following text*

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 862492.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency. This does not, however, give them the right of exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark of logo, either by registration of by any other means.

2. Monitoring and reporting

Following a specific methodology applied to all European Projects, EUT Research Communication Office has prepared an excel file to register all dissemination and communication activities done by partners during project execution.

This file, located in Sharepoint online repository to be available to all partners (05_Dissemination and visual identity - 00_Reporting Dissemination Activities) contains, among others, a description of dissemination activity, type of audience, date and location, partner involved, feedback received and information about which WP / Task was covered in dissemination.

Table 3: Table to record communication and dissemination activities

Dates	Type of dissemination action <i>Select from breakdown list</i>	Event name / description of the audience <i>Select from breakdown list</i>	Type of audience <i>Select from breakdown list</i>	Size of audience (estimated number of persons reached)	Country	City	WP / Task covered in Dissemination	Overview feedback received	Partner involved <i>Select from breakdown list</i>	Proof of material <i>External link / link to shared folder</i>

Nombre	Modificado	Modificado por	+ Agregar columna
KPI_Reporting_MADRAS.xlsx	Hace unos segundos	Marina Presas Quintana	

2.1 Communication KPIs

The following table introduces an initial set of MADRAS Key performance Indicators (KPIs) for assessing the communication activities. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

Table 4: Communication KPIs

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	Target by the end of the project
Media	Number of press releases	Proof of publication and reporting in reports / project meetings	>2
	Number of articles published		>30
Website	Number of web visits	Matomo Analytis	>4.000
	Number Pages Viewed		>10.000
	Number page / session		>1.5
	Number users		>2.000
	Avg. session time		>3.00 min (70% of the users)
Social Media - Twitter	Number Followers	Twitter Analytics	>200
	Number Tweets		>150
	Twitter Impressions		>50.000
	Number mentions		>20
Social Media - YouTube	Number of videos uploaded	Proof of publication in reports	>2

Social Media - Partners	Number of posts in corporate channels	Monthly follow up (quantitative)	>20
	Number of Likes in corporate channels		>50
	Number Shares / Retweets in corporate channels		>10
	Participation in LinkedIn groups		Proof of publication

2.2 KPIs reporting

Progress until the end of the project will be reported in **Deliverables 5.12, 5.13, 5.14, 5.15**, Outreach reports, as well as in interim progress reports.

To facilitate the reporting, an excel file has been prepared to record monthly the KPIs progress. The file, stored in Sharepoint Collaborative Platform (05_Dissemination and visual identity - 00_Reporting Dissemination Activities) includes the following tabs related to communication activities:

- **Web and SM:** to report progress on project and partners channels
- **Media Clipping:** for recording articles in generalist and specialised media outlets
- **Blog posts:** tracking the status of partners blog posts to be published on the website

KPIs MADRAS Digital Channels	april 2020	may-20	jun-20	jul-20	ago-20	sept-20	oct-20
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7
Twitter Corporate Account							
# Followers							
# New Followers							
# Total Tweets							
# New Tweets							
# Twitter Impressions							
# Mentions							
# Likes on Tweets							
# Retweets							
Twitter Accounts Partners							
EUT							
GNK							
AWF							
UPA							
UWL							
TNG							
UNE							
TNO							
INF							
EFC							
TOTAL (aggregate)							
Web (MATOMO Analytics)							
# Web Visits	NA	NA	NA				
Avg. session time	NA	NA	NA				
# Pages Viewed	NA	NA	NA				
# Actions / Session	NA	NA	NA				
# Users	NA	NA	NA				
# Downloads	NA	NA	NA				

Figure 9: View of the file for reporting Social Media and Website statistics

Communication Activities Calendar

COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
MADRAS	abr-20	may-20	jun-20	jul-20	ago-20	sep-20	oct-20	nov-20	dec-20	jan-20	feb-21	mar-21
Project templates (presentation + agenda / deliverable template)	X											
Visual Identity Manual		X										
Creation of Twitter account		X										
Webiste Content		X	X									
Set up excel files and structure to report on communication activities			X									
Social Media Plan			X									
Update Twitter Account			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Website Set up			X									
D5.9 Visual Corporate Image			X									
D5.11 Communication Activities			X									
D.5.10 Project Public Page			X									
Website Update				X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Press release Project kick-off				X								
Newsletter sign up form ready and published on the webiste				X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Infosheet content ready					X							
Flyer content ready					X							
Rollup content ready					X							

Poster template ready						X							
General Project presentation							X						
Flyer design							X						
Rollup design							X						
Infosheet design							X						
Creation of YouTube Channel												X	
Animated video													X
D5.15 Communication Materials													X
	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	
	abr-21	may-21	jun-21	jul-21	ago-21	sep-21	oct-21	nov-21	dec-21	jan-22	feb-22	mar-22	
Update Twitter Account	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Website update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
1st Newsletter	X												
2 nd Newsletter						X							
Video interviews to partners for Social Media	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Videos on MADRAS experiments and production process						X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Press release materials developed													X
	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	
	abr-22	may-22	jun-22	jul-22	ago-22	sep-22	oct-22	nov-22	dec-22	jan-23	feb-23	mar-23	

MADRAS

Update Twitter Account	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Website update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Videos on MADRAS experiments and production process	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
3rd Newsletter	X											
4th Newsletter						X						
D5.13 Communication Activities Report Update						X						
Update Project flyer & infosheet						X						
5th Newsletter										X		
Press Release Business Case eCooltra										X		
Press Release Business Case UWINLOC										X		
Press Release end of the project - results												X
6th Newsletter												X
D5.14 Communication Activities Report Update												X

